

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE OF IMPLEMENTING INNOVATIVE PROCESSES IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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ABSTRACT

The article covers the foreign experiences of implementing innovative processes in industrial enterprises and briefly describes the main tools used in it. Also, suggestions and conclusions are given regarding the feasibility of applying advanced foreign experience in practice.

The practice of economically developed countries shows that in modern conditions, sustainable economic growth is associated with a high level of introduction of new technologies and developments in production. According to various estimates, from 50 to 70 percent of GDP production growth in these countries comes from innovations. is provided at the expense of use.

In order to regulate innovative processes, the state directly and indirectly supports innovative activities.

Globalization determines the paradigm of innovative economic growth if the rational mobilization of resources and factors of the world economy affects the quantitative parameters of development. should be used relatively actively.

At the same time, innovative processes and their impact on the state of

the economy and society are characterized by significant differences.

The management system directly differs from the management of the innovation process itself and other socio-economic processes by its goals, content, tasks, principles and methods. The goals of the management of the innovation process are as follows:

- to constantly update the assortment and nomenclature of products, as well as the used equipment, technology, production organization methods;

- further development of the country's scientific and scientific-technical potential, creation of scientific foundations.

In general, the main components of the innovation process can be shown as follows (Table 1):

The main components of the innovation process

Innovation is a new idea, new knowledge	New ideas that can be obtained as a result of scientific research (fundamental and practical), experimental developments, and other types of creative and intellectual activity
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Innovations or innovations	Implementation of innovation, i.e. achieving practical application of new knowledge to meet specific needs
Diffusion of innovation	Dissemination of acquired innovation, i.e. application of innovative products, services and technologies in new places and conditions.

Effective management of the innovation process is achieved through the innovation mechanism.

Innovative mechanism is a combination of organizational management, financial-economic legal information, technical and spiritual-psychological factors, their interdependence and interaction contribute to the successful implementation of innovative activities.

In practice, the use of variants of forms of organization of innovative processes is determined by three factors.

- the state of the external environment and the economic situation, the type of market, the nature of competition, the practice of regulating the state monopoly, etc.;

- a specific economic system, the state of the internal environment (the political presence of the entrepreneur-leader and support group, the amount of financial and material resources used in technology, the existing organizational structure, the internal culture of the organization, relations with other organizations, the environment, etc.);

- the uniqueness of the innovation process as a management object.

Innovative processes are considered as processes that cover all scientific and technical production and marketing activities of manufacturers and are ultimately aimed at meeting market needs.

Organization of innovations in industrial enterprises is research on the new direction of scientific thinking. In order to introduce innovations in industrial enterprises, it is necessary to determine the socio-economic effectiveness of new technology, develop a methodology for

managing scientific and technical progress and efficiency.

The innovative way of development requires the activation of industrial activity at the level of economic entities - this is the creation of investments in relevant scientific and technical developments.

In order to start introducing innovations in the context of industrial activity, the following factors should be taken into account:

- consider innovations as a continuous process;

- to pay attention to the controllability of the process, that is, the ability to influence it;

- the existence of general relationships between the factors and conditions of innovation at the level of an industrial enterprise.

Such an approach allows to reorganize enterprises on the basis of high-tech production. The innovation process consists of several stages, which together form the life cycle of an innovative product.

Among other types of innovation, there are five stages of the composition and content of the stages of the innovation process in relation to product innovation, which is the most important:

In Western Europe, the USA and Japan, fundamental science is mainly based on higher education. In Russia - in network and economic institutes. Research institutes (ITIs) separated from higher education institutions and enterprises remain the main form of organization of scientific research in Russia. The Russian Academy of Sciences occupies a leading position in the network of scientific organizations with an academic profile. The result of fundamental scientific research is new theoretical knowledge-

discoveries. Statistical data show that only 10 percent of fundamental research has a positive result. In the United States, universities are the most important for fundamental research. 51.3% of the research, the role of university science in fulfilling the orders of the National Institute of Health is especially large - 66.7%, the Pentagon allocates 48.7% of basic research to universities.

In order to manage the innovative activity of the enterprise and to choose the most effective means of evaluating the innovative potential, it is necessary to develop ways to increase the innovative activity in the enterprises of the industrial sector.

In order to create an effective model of introducing innovations in a production enterprise, it is necessary to evaluate the following indicators:

-competitiveness, efficiency, source of origin, source of financing, level of risk, source of creation, costs.

The practical use of this result in production is not always predictable and the probability of getting a negative result is high. That is why investments in practical research are considered risky.

3. Development (design) stage.

This stage includes the preparation of the design for further production of the product.

This includes the following key activities:

1. Engineering forecasting - forecasting new technical solutions, new materials, new design methods.

2. Parametric optimization - determining the technical characteristics of the product sample, ensuring the optimal range of product parameters and its standard dimensions.

3. Determination of technical alternatives for the development of a product design-project, verification of the suitability of the development of the technical design for the production of the product.

4. Prototype production testing and adjustment.

5. Design documentation based on the results of prototype testing.

In other words, there is often a significant time gap between the first two components of the innovation process - innovation and innovation, which slows down the entire innovation process.

Depending on what is the starting point of the innovation process, two main types of linear models can be distinguished.

Within the framework of linear models of innovation processes, regardless of the source of innovation, the sequence of stages is expressed as a chain of connections, that is, if the results of one stage are inputs, it has a linear character.

In modern conditions, ensuring the innovative direction of industrial enterprises increases the consumption of manufactured products and contributes to the balance and efficiency of the entire market. With such an approach, innovation can be considered the key to sustainable economic development.

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